

1 **Supplementary Information**

2

3 **μ -opioid receptor-mediated downregulation of midline thalamic pathways**
4 **to basal and central amygdala**

5

6 Goedecke L.*, Bengoetxea X., Blaesse P., Pape H.-C., and Juengling K.

7

8 Affiliation: Institute of Physiology I, Westfaelische Wilhelms-Universitaet Muenster,
9 Germany

10 *Correspondence: lena.goedecke@ukmuenster.de

11

12

1 Supplementary Figures

2

3

4 **Supplementary Figure 1.** MORs in the dMT.

5 (A) DAPI staining illustrates distribution of cell nuclei in the dMT. MOR labeling reveals a
6 strong and uniform MOR-IR in the dMT. Scale bars represent 100 μm .

7 (B) Representative traces of responses to hyper- and depolarizing current steps of increasing
8 amplitude (-60 pA, -20 pA, 0 pA, +20 pA, +60 pA) from -60 mV in a dMT neuron during
9 baseline, maximal DAMGO effect and wash.

10 (C) The apparent input resistance was calculated from the voltage-deflection in response to
11 the -60 pA hyperpolarizing current step. During maximal effect the cell was manually
12 clamped back to -60 mV to exclude a possible influence of voltage-dependent conductances
13 on the input resistance (n = 23 cells/9 mice). MOR activation reduced the apparent input
14 resistance of dMT neurons projecting to BA and CeL.

1

2 **Supplementary Figure 2.** Characterization of dMT-BA and dMT-CeL projection patterns
 3 and synaptic transmission.

4 (A) Histology and schematic presentation of AAV2-ChR2-eYFP injection sites in the dMT in
 5 five mice included in the analysis (#7650-7654).

6 (B) ChR2-eYFP expressing dMT projections in BA and CeL. For each mouse, recordings
 7 were initiated in that brain slice exhibiting most prominent expression of labeled fibers which
 8 is displayed here. Number of recorded neurons that received AMPAR-mediated oEPSCS
 9 versus non-responding cells in CeL and BA.

10 (C) Tbr1-IR marks PN of cortical origin and thereby distinguishes basolateral (LA and BA)
 11 from central amygdala (CeL and CeM). ChR2-eYFP expressing dMT projections are

- 1 especially dense in the CeL and anterior portion of the BA (aBA) but not in the LA or
- 2 posterior BA (pBA).
- 3 (D) Representative trace of dMT-driven PSCs in BA PNs at a holding potential of -45 mV.
- 4 (E) Absolute oPSC amplitudes: Light stimulation of dMT projections in the BA evoked
- 5 monosynaptic oEPSC in all cells but never polysynaptic oIPSCs (n = 11 cells/2 mice).
- 6 Scale bars represent 100 μ m.
- 7

1

2 **Supplementary Figure 3.** The DAMGO-induced inhibition of dMT inputs to BA PNs is
3 dependent on opioid receptors.

4 (A) In the absence of DAMGO, oEPSC amplitudes are constant over the time course of the
5 recording. Mean normalized oEPSC amplitudes in BA PNs under control conditions without
6 DAMGO application (n = 14 cells/5 mice) in comparison to oEPSCs in BA PNs
7 (n = 11 cells/7 mice) before, during, and after DAMGO application (horizontal line). The data
8 set of oEPSCs in BA PNs under DAMGO (grey) is the same as shown in Fig. 3C.

9 (B) Quantification of the mean normalized oEPSC amplitudes in BA PNs under control
10 conditions at 1-5 mins, 10-15 mins, and 20-25 mins. Control BA PNs did not exhibit a
11 reduction in oEPSC amplitude as it was seen during maximal DAMGO effect (10-15 mins)
12 and washout (20-25 mins) for BA PNs after DAMGO application.

13 (C) DAMGO-induced reduction in oEPSC amplitudes is fully reversed by application of the
14 non-selective opioid receptor antagonist Naloxone. Mean normalized oEPSC amplitudes in

1 BA PNs during baseline, DAMGO application, and washout in 1 μ M Naloxone in comparison
2 to washout in ACSF (data set in grey from Fig. 3C and Fig. S3A).

3 (D) Quantification of the mean normalized oEPSC amplitudes in BA PNs at 1-4 mins,
4 9-12 mins, and 20-23 mins. oEPSC amplitudes in BA PNs were attenuated following
5 DAMGO and fully recovered during washout in Naloxone (n = 10 cells/3 mice).

6

1

2 **Supplementary Figure 4.** Schematic presentation of two MOR modulated pathways
 3 projecting onto CeM output neurons.

4 In a very simplified scenario, two independent pathways project onto a CeM output neuron.
 5 The first one (1) consists of glutamatergic dMT inputs that drive feedforward excitation via
 6 BA principal neurons. In the second pathway (2), glutamatergic BA principal neurons, which
 7 might differ from BA PNs of the first circuit, project onto intercalated cells of the
 8 medioventral cluster (mITC(v)), triggering feedforward inhibition of the CeM neuron ¹⁹. A
 9 broad activation of MORs in both pathways should reduce both, feedforward excitation and
 10 inhibition, with limited net effect in the CeM neuron. In the CeM output neuron, general
 11 synaptic activity would be reduced without a shift of the excitation/inhibition ratio. This
 12 would only be valid for this reductionist scheme with only one driving input in both pathways
 13 and the assumption that inhibitory and excitatory inputs have comparable magnitude. If one
 14 considers that multiple glutamatergic inputs can drive feedforward inhibition via mITC(v)s
 15 and feedforward excitation via BA PNs, the situation might be very different. In this scenario,
 16 the somatic, inhibitory effect of MOR activation in mITC(v)s (2) might be much more
 17 effective, switching off feedforward inhibition driven by multiple sources. On the other hand,
 18 feedforward excitation might be less affected, since not all inputs on BA PNs are modulated
 19 by MOR (1). In that pathway, MOR activation reduces the excitatory drive of a fraction of
 20 inputs, leaving others unaffected. In that scenario, broad, synchronized MOR activation might
 21 shift the excitation/inhibition ratio in CeM neurons in favor of excitation. Whether such a
 22 synchronized MOR activation occurs *in vivo* is not clear, but it seems more likely that MOR
 23 activation in the different pathways is much more diverse, depending e.g. on the behavioral
 24 context and activated sources of endogenous opioids.

1 **Supplementary Methods**

2 *Animals and Ethical Approval.*

3 Adult C57BL/6J mice used had access to food and water ad libitum at a 12 h light/dark cycle
4 with lights on at 6:00 am. All animal experiments were performed in accordance with
5 European regulations on animal experimentation (Directive 2010/63/EU of the European
6 parliament and the council) and protocols were approved by the local authorities
7 (Bezirksregierung Münster and the 'Landesamt für Natur, Umwelt und Verbraucherschutz
8 Nordrhein-Westfalen').

9 *Retrograde Tracing and Viral Transduction.*

10 For retrograde tracing experiments, CTB-A1488 was diluted to a working concentration of
11 0.5 % (w/v) in 0.1 M phosphate-buffered saline (PBS). 100 nL CTB-A1488 was delivered
12 locally into the CeL or BA of C57BL/6J mice by stereotaxic injection. Viral transduction of
13 neurons in the dMT was performed using 300 nL rAAV2-hSyn-hChR2-eYFP. Coordinates
14 for CeL injection were -1.65 mm anteroposterior (AP), ± 3.00 mm mediolateral (ML), and
15 3.90 mm dorsoventral (DV) according to bregma. BA coordinates were -1.65 mm AP,
16 ± 3.30 mm ML, and 4.10 mm DV. dMT coordinates were -0.60 mm AP, 0.30 mm ML, and
17 3.15 mm DV. dMT injections were conducted in a 5° angle ML to prevent damage of the
18 *sinus sagittalis superior*. Prior to stereotaxic surgery, mice were anesthetized with an
19 intraperitoneal injection of sodium pentobarbital (50 mg/kg), along with subcutaneously
20 injected Carprofen (5 mg/kg, Rimadyl, Pfizer) as an analgesic. The surgery was performed
21 according to standard protocols. A 10 μ l Hamilton syringe with a 33 gauge beveled needle
22 was moved with a micromanipulator, and served to deliver the retrograde tracer or rAAV into
23 the brain. Following manual injection, the needle was left in place for 10 min and was then
24 carefully and slowly pulled out. 3-4 days following the surgical procedure,
25 electrophysiological recordings were performed on retrogradely labeled neurons in the dMT.
26 Optogenetic experiments were carried out 5-7 weeks following surgery.

27 *Electrophysiology and Optogenetic Stimulation.*

28 Mice were anesthetized in isoflurane (2.5 % in O₂, AbbVie) and decapitated. After surgical
29 extraction of the brain, 300 μ m thick coronal slices were cut on a vibratome (VT 1200 S,
30 Leica). For whole-cell patch-clamp recordings, brain slices were placed in a submersion
31 chamber and perfused with artificial cerebrospinal fluid (aCSF) composed of (in mM)

1 120 NaCl, 2.5 KCl, 1.25 NaH₂PO₄, 2 MgSO₄, 2 CaCl₂, 22 NaHCO₃, and 25 glucose at 32°C.
2 The pH was adjusted to 7.35 by gassing with carbogen. The ion channel blockers TTX (1 μM,
3 Biotrend), 4-AP (100 μM), DNQX (10 μM), AP-5 (50 μM), gabazine (25 μM), and
4 CGP55845 (10 μM) were added to the aCSF when required (Abcam). Borosilicate glass
5 capillaries (Harvard Apparatus) were used as recording pipettes (2-4 MΩ) and filled with an
6 internal solution containing (in mM) 10 NaCl, 88 potassium gluconate, 20 potassium citrate,
7 10 HEPES, 3 BAPTA, 15 phosphocreatine, 1 MgCl₂, 0.5 CaCl₂, 3 Mg-ATP, and 0.5 Na-GTP.
8 All electrophysiological data were acquired at a sampling rate of 10 kHz with an EPC-10
9 patch-clamp amplifier in combination with the software Pulse (HEKA) and analyzed offline
10 in Clampfit 9.2 (Molecular Devices). The series resistance was monitored throughout the
11 recordings and data were discarded when sudden changes occurred. The specific MOR
12 agonist D-Ala²-NMe-Phe⁴-Gly-o⁵-enkephalin (DAMGO, R&D Systems) was bath-applied
13 for 5 min at a flow rate of 3-3.5 mL/min and a concentration of 250 nM.

14 *Membrane potential and input resistance of dMT neurons.* Retrogradely traced neurons in the
15 dMT after BA or CeA injection of CTB-A1488 were identified by their somatic fluorescence.
16 The membrane potential was recorded in current-clamp mode in aCSF containing DNQX and
17 AP-5 to block glutamatergic, and gabazine, and CGP55845 to block GABAergic synaptic
18 transmission. To ensure comparable ionic driving forces for all dMT neurons, the membrane
19 potential was adjusted to approximately -60 mV before recording baseline. Current-voltage
20 relationships (current pulse duration: 500 ms, maximal hyperpolarizing pulse: -60 pA,
21 increment: 10 pA) were measured during baseline, maximal effect, and washout of DAMGO
22 to assess changes in input resistance. During maximal effect, a direct current offset was
23 applied to set back the membrane potential to -60 mV, in order to exclude voltage-dependent
24 conductance contributing to changes in input resistance and thus, to isolate direct DAMGO-
25 induced effects.

26 *Optogenetically evoked excitatory postsynaptic currents in BA PNs and CeL neurons.* In order
27 to study dMT synaptic inputs to BA and CeL neurons, we used an optogenetic approach.
28 ChR2-eYFP expressing axonal projections in the amygdala were stimulated using microscope
29 objective-coupled LEDs (460 nm, 45 mW, Prizmatix). 10-20 light stimuli were applied at 15 s
30 intervals and evoked excitatory postsynaptic currents (oEPSCs) in BA and CeL neurons
31 recorded in voltage-clamp mode at a holding potential of -65 mV or produced failures. A
32 failure was assigned, when the current deflection upon light stimulus was smaller than the
33 noise of the recording. The mean noise for recordings at -65 mV in BA and CeL neurons was
34 10.3 ± 0.5 pA. Failures per total number of light stimuli (10-20) were expressed as failure rate

1 and remaining success oEPSC amplitudes were averaged. In some cells, the paired pulse ratio
2 was assessed on the basis of two light stimuli at 10 Hz at an inter-stimulus interval of 15 s.
3 Gabazine and CGP55845 were added to the aCSF, and TTX and 4-AP were present to block
4 polysynaptic transmission¹. After recording the AMPAR-mediated component of the oEPSCs
5 at -65 mV, we clamped the same cell at a depolarized membrane potential of +40 mV to
6 assess the NMDAR-mediated component of the oEPSC. To allow voltage clamp recordings at
7 +40 mV, potassium currents were blocked using a cesium-based internal solution, containing
8 (in mM) 5 4-AP, 120 CsMeSO₄, 1 EGTA, 10 HEPES, 20 tetraethylammonium chloride,
9 2 MgCl₂, 0.5 CaCl₂, 2 Na-ATP, and 0.5 Na-GTP. The mean noise of recordings at +40 mV
10 was 19.5 ± 1.2 pA and smaller oEPSC amplitudes were considered failures. While the
11 amplitude of the AMPAR-mediated oEPSC was always determined at the peak of the oEPSC
12 at -65 mV, the amplitude of the longer-lasting NMDA component was determined at 95 ms
13 post light-stimulation. At that point in time the AMPAR component had declined to zero. In
14 addition to the absolute amplitudes of AMPAR- and NMDAR-mediated oEPSCs, their ratio
15 was compared for CeL and BA neurons (oEPSC_{-65mV}/oEPSC_{+40mV}). Furthermore, dMT-CeL
16 and dMT-BA apparent connectivity, i.e. the quotient of neurons receiving light-evoked input
17 divided by the total number of neurons patched, was compared. In these experiments and
18 when absolute oEPSC amplitudes and failure rates of dMT-BA and dMT-CeL synapses were
19 compared, light-stimulation was kept constant at 1 ms pulse duration and 14 mW. The
20 localization of recorded CeL and BA neurons and the corresponding size of the oEPSC
21 amplitude were documented. Neurons were mapped at the tip of the recording electrode in the
22 slice and pictures were overlaid manually. For *post hoc* identification, cells were filled with
23 neurobiotin during some of the recordings. In order to study dMT-driven feedforward
24 inhibition onto BA PNs, we further recorded BA PNs at a holding potential of -45 mV,
25 positive to the reversal potential of GABA receptor-mediated inhibitory currents (E_{GABA}), to
26 obtain biphasic responses composed of monosynaptic oEPSCs and disynaptic oIPSCs. A
27 potassium gluconate internal solution and aCSF without synaptic blockers were used as
28 described before. Following synaptic characterization, AMPAR-mediated oEPSCs were
29 recorded in BA PNs and CeL neurons at -65 mV and the effect of MOR stimulation on mean
30 normalized oEPSC amplitudes and failure rates was analyzed before DAMGO (baseline),
31 during maximal DAMGO response and following wash. For each timepoint, responses to a
32 series of 20 light stimuli were analyzed and success amplitudes were averaged. To confirm
33 that DAMGO-induced effects are dependent on opioid receptors, the non-selective opioid
34 receptor antagonist Naloxone (Naloxone hydrochloride, R&D Systems) was bath-applied

1 following DAMGO administration and during wash at a concentration of 1 μ M in some
2 experiments.
3 *dMT-driven feedforward excitation of CeM.* To study feedforward excitation of CeM neurons,
4 dMT axonal projections in the BA were stimulated with 10 light-pulses at 50 Hz at an interval
5 of 15 s. oEPSCs were recorded at -65 mV holding potential in an aCSF containing
6 1.2 mM CaCl₂ and 1 mM MgSO₄ to increase neuronal excitability. GABA_{A/B}R blocker were
7 contained in the aCSF and the recording pipette was filled with potassium-based internal
8 solution. The total charge transfer during the multiple oEPSCs, as well as amplitude and
9 failure rate of the first oEPSC were analyzed during baseline, maximal DAMGO effect, and
10 washout in BA PNs.

11 *Fluorescence detection and immunohistochemistry*

12 For *post hoc* verification and documentation of the AAV2-ChR2-eYFP and CTB-A1488
13 injection and recording sites, acute slice preparations were fixed in 4 % paraformaldehyde in
14 0.15 M Na-phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) at 4°C for 24 hours and cryoprotected in 30 % sucrose
15 in PBS. 40 μ m thick sections were prepared and mounted in DAPI
16 (4',6-Diamino-2-phenylindole dihydrochloride)-containing Vectashield Mounting Medium
17 (Vector Laboratories) without further immunohistochemical staining. When cells were filled
18 with neurobiotin during the recording, 300 μ m thick slices were kept and blocked for 1 hour
19 in 3 % bovine serum albumin (BSA), 10 % goat serum, and 0.3 % Triton in PBS. After three
20 wash steps in PBS, slices were incubated in blocking solution containing a streptavidin Alexa
21 Fluor 546 conjugate (1:1,250, Life Technologies) for 2 hours.

22 Tbr1, a marker of glutamatergic neurons² was detected using a polyclonal rabbit anti-Tbr1
23 antibody (1 mg/ml; ab 31940; Abcam). Immunohistochemical stainings were performed on
24 acute slices expressing ChR2-eYFP-positive fibers from the dMT in the BA and CeL.

25 Following recordings, slices were fixed and cryoprotected as described above and 30 μ m
26 thick sections were cut. Sections were collected in 15 % sucrose/PBS, followed by three
27 washes in PBS and were blocked for 1 hour. The anti-Tbr1 antibody was diluted 1:1,000 in
28 blocking solution and incubation with agitation was carried out at 4°C overnight. After three
29 wash steps in PBS, sections were incubated in carrier solution (0.3 % Triton, 1 % BSA, 1 %
30 goat serum) containing the secondary antibody Alexa Fluor 546 goat anti-rabbit (2 mg/ml;
31 1:1,000 ; Life Technologies) for 2 hours at RT.

32 Immunohistochemical detection of the μ -opioid receptor was performed using a rabbit anti-
33 MOR antibody (OPRM1 antibody; 24216, Origene Europe, Herford, Germany)³. In brief,

1 mice were anesthetized with isoflurane (5 %) and perfused transcardially with phosphate-
2 buffered saline (pH 7.4; PBS), followed by 4 % paraformaldehyde (w/v) and 15 % saturated
3 picric acid (v/v) in 0.15 M Na-phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) as fixative. After removal, brains
4 were stored in fixative for 2 hours at RT. Brains were cryoprotected in a sucrose solution as
5 described above and coronal sections (30 μ m) were cut using a freezing microtome
6 (Frigomobil 1205; Jung, Heidelberg, Germany). Sections were collected in 15 %
7 sucrose/PBS, then blocked and incubated with the primary and secondary antibodies as
8 described above. The anti-MOR antibody was diluted 1:1,000 in blocking solution. The
9 secondary antibody goat anti-rabbit conjugated to AlexaFluor 488 was diluted 1:1,000
10 (LifeTechnologies) in carrier solution.
11 Cell nuclei were labelled using DAPI (1:1,000, Sigma-Aldrich) and after three additional
12 washes in PBS, sections were mounted with Vectashield HardSet mounting medium (Vector
13 laboratories, Burlingame, CA) or sections were directly mounted in DAPI-containing
14 Vectashield Mounting Medium.
15 Imaging was performed on a laser scanning confocal microscope (Nikon eC1plus) equipped
16 with a CFI75 LWD 16 \times /0.8NA or CFI Plan Fluor 10 \times /0.30NA objective (Nikon, Germany).
17 Channels were imaged sequentially with 405 nm, 488 nm and/or 543 nm excitation in
18 combination with adequate emission filters (450/30 nm, 515/30 nm, and 605/75, respectively)
19 to prevent bleed-through. Images were further processed with ImageJ
20 (<http://rsb.info.nih.gov/ij>).

21 *Statistics.*

22 Data are shown as box plots. The box represents the first (25 %) and third (75 %) quartile, the
23 whiskers represent the 5 % and 95 % percentiles. The band inside the box represents the
24 median, the square represents the mean. In scatter plots, whiskers represent the standard error.
25 All data sets were tested for statistically significant outliers at a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$
26 using the Grubb's test. Data were tested for Gaussian distribution using the Shapiro-Wilk test
27 at a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$. Within-group comparisons were done with paired student's
28 t-test and differences between two different groups were analyzed with the unpaired t-test.
29 Statistics for not normally distributed values were done using the Mann-Whitney rank sum
30 test. Significant differences between three different groups were accessed using one-way
31 ANOVA with Bonferroni *post hoc* test. To analyze significant differences between correlated
32 samples and control for within-subject differences, repeated measures ANOVA with
33 Bonferroni *post hoc* test was applied.

1 **References**

- 2 1. Cruikshank, S. J., Urabe, H., Nurmikko, A. V. & Connors, B. W. Pathway-specific
3 feedforward circuits between thalamus and neocortex revealed by selective optical
4 stimulation of axons. *Neuron* **65**, 230–245 (2010).
5
- 6 2. Waclaw, R. R., Ehrman, L. A., Pierani, A. & Campbell, K. Developmental Origin of the
7 Neuronal Subtypes That Comprise the Amygdalar Fear Circuit in the Mouse. *J. Neurosci.*
8 **30**, 6944–6953 (2010).
9
- 10 3. Arvidsson, U. *et al.* Distribution and targeting of a mu-opioid receptor (MOR1) in brain
11 and spinal cord. *J. Neurosci.* **15**, 3328–3341 (1995).
12